

A Comparison between the Variational Iteration Method and the Homotopy Perturbation Method for the Burgers - Huxley Equation

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Date:

6 February 2016

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Abstract: *In this paper, the Variational Iteration Method (VIM) and the Homotopy Perturbation Method (HPM) are applied to solve the Burgers - Huxley non-linear differential equations. A comparison is made between obtained results in finding the exact solution of the equation in order to present precision of the methods. The study reveals that the methods are effective and convenient techniques to solve the Burgers – Huxley equation. Also, results prove capability and great potential of the methods as effective algorithms in order to obtain the exact solution of non-linear differential equations.*

Keywords: Burgers – Huxley equation, Variational Iteration Method, Homotopy Perturbation Method, Nonlinear differential equations

1. Introduction

Nonlinear differential equations can model many phenomena in different fields of science and engineering in order to present their behaviors and effects by mathematical concepts. Most of the equations do not have analytical solution which can be handled by semi-analytical methods.

In order to obtain exact solution of nonlinear differential equations, semi-analytical methods such as the Variational Iteration Method (VIM) and Homotopy Perturbation Method (HPM) are considered. The ideas of the VIM and HPM were first pioneered by He [1], [2]. The VIM is applied by He [3], [4] in order to solve autonomous ordinary differential equation as well as delay differential equation. Also, He [5] presented application of the HPM in solving the non-linear non-homogeneous partial differential equations. They are powerful algorithms in solving various kinds of linear and nonlinear equations.

The homotopy perturbation method is used by Nourazar et al. [6], [7], [8] in order to obtain exact solution of nonlinear differential equations. Batiha et al. [9] presented application of variational iteration method to the generalized Burgers–Huxley equation. Abzari and Abzari [10] presented numerical study of Burgers–Huxley equations via reduced differential transform method. Comparative analysis of variational iteration method and Haar wavelet method for the numerical solutions of Burgers–Huxley and Huxley equations is presented by Ray and Gupta [11]. Soori et al. [12], [13] presented application of the Variational Iteration Method and the Homotopy Perturbation Method to the fisher type equation. Also, Soori [14] presented Series Solution of Weakly-Singular Kernel Volterra Integro-Differential equations by the Combined Laplace-Adomian Method.

Application of the Variational Iteration Method for the Newell-Whitehead-Segel Equation is presented by Soori [15].

The Burgers equation was first introduced in order to describe turbulence in one space dimension. Also, it is used to model several physical contexts such as the interaction between reaction mechanisms, convection effects and diffusion transport, nerve pulse propagation in nerve fibers as well as wall motion in liquid crystals.

The generalized Burgers - Huxley equation investigated by Satsuma [16] is written as:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - \alpha u^n \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \beta u(1 - u^n)(u^n - \gamma), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, t \geq 0, \quad (1.1)$$

Where $\alpha, \beta \geq 0$ are real constants and n is a positive integer and $\gamma \in [0, 1]$. Eq. (1.1) models the interaction between reaction mechanisms, convection effects and diffusion transports [16].

When $\alpha = 0$ and $n = 1$, Eq. (1.1) is reduced to the Huxley equation which describes nerve pulse propagation in nerve fibers and wall motion in liquid crystals [17]. When $\beta = 0$ and $n = 1$, Eq. (1.1) is reduced to the Burgers equation describing the far field of wave propagation in nonlinear dissipative systems [18]. When $n = 1, \alpha \neq 0$ and $\beta \neq 0$, the Eq. (1.1) is turned into the Burgers-Huxley equation.

In the present research work, the Variational Iteration Method (VIM) and the Homotopy Perturbation Method (HPM) are applied to obtain the closed form solution of the non-linear Burgers - Huxley equation. The trend of rapid convergence of the sequences constructed by the VIM and HPM toward the exact solution of the equation are also numerically presented. As a result, a comparison between obtained results by the methods is presented in order to show their accuracy and reliability in solving the equation.

The ideas of variational iteration method as well as homotopy perturbation method are presented in the section 2 and section 3 respectively. Application of the variational iteration method and the homotopy perturbation method to the exact solution of Burgers - Huxley equation is presented in the section 4.

2. The idea of variational iteration method

The idea of the variational iteration method is based on constructing a correction functional by a general Lagrange multiplier. The multiplier is chosen in such a way that its correction solution is improved with respect to the initial approximation or to the trial function. To illustrate the basic idea of the variational iteration method, consider the following nonlinear equation:

$$Lu(t) + Nu(t) = g(t), \quad (2.1)$$

Where L is a linear operator, N is a nonlinear operator, and $g(t)$ is a known analytic function. According to the variational iteration method, we can construct the following correction functional:

$$u_{n+1}(x, t) = u_n(x, t) + \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) (Lu_n(\xi) + N\tilde{u}_n(\xi) - g(\xi)) d\xi, \quad (2.2)$$

Where λ is a general Lagrange multiplier which can be identified optimally via variational theory and $\tilde{u}_n$ is considered as a restricted variation which means $\delta\tilde{u}_n = 0$.

$u_0(t)$ is an initial approximation with possible unknowns. We first determine the Lagrange multiplier λ that will be identified optimally via integration by parts. With λ determined, then several approximations $u_n(t), n \geq 0$ follow immediately. Consequently, the exact solution may be obtained as:

$$u(t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n(t), \quad (2.3)$$

The correction functional of the Eq. (2.1) gives several approximations. Therefore, the exact solution can be obtained as the limit of resulting successive approximations.

3. The idea of homotopy perturbation method

The homotopy perturbation method (HPM) is originally initiated by He [2]. This is a combination of the classical perturbation technique and homotopy technique. The basic idea of the HPM for solving nonlinear differential equations is as follow; consider the following differential equation:

$$E(u) = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

Where E is any differential operator. We construct a homotopy as follow:

$$H(u, p) = (1 - p)F(u) + p(E(u) - F(u)). \quad (3.2)$$

Where $F(u)$ is a functional operator with the known solution v_0 . It is clear that when p is equal to zero then $H(u, 0) = F(u) = 0$, and when p is equal to 1, then $H(u, 1) = E(u) = 0$. It is worth noting that as the embedding parameter p increases monotonically from zero to unity the zero order solution v_0 continuously deforms into the original problem $E(u) = 0$. The embedding parameter, $p \in [0, 1]$, is considered as an expanding parameter [5]. In the homotopy perturbation method the embedding parameter p is used to get series expansion for solution as:

$$u = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} p^i v_i = v_0 + p v_1 + p^2 v_2 + p^3 v_3 + \dots \quad (3.3)$$

When $p \rightarrow 1$, then Eq. (3.2) becomes the approximate solution to Eq. (3.1) as:

$$u = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 + \dots \quad (3.4)$$

The series Eq. (3.4) is a convergent series and the rate of convergence depends on the nature of Eq. (3.1) [2,5]. It is also assumed that Eq. (3.2) has a unique solution and by comparing the like powers of p the solution of various orders is obtained. These solutions are obtained using the Maple package.

4. The Burgers – Huxley equation

The Burgers – Huxley equation for $\alpha = 0$, $n = 1$, $\gamma = 1$, $\beta = 1$, is constructed as Eq. (4.1) in order to present the capability and reliability of the methods.

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + u(1-u)(u-1), \quad (4.1)$$

Subject to initial condition:

$$u(x, 0) = \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}, \quad (4.2)$$

4.1. The variational iteration method:

The correction functional for Eq. (4.1) is in the following form:

$$u_{n+1}(x, t) = u_n(x, t) + \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + u_n(x, \xi) - 2u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi \quad (4.3)$$

Where u_n is restricted variation $\delta u_n = 0$, λ is a Lagrange multiplier and u_0 is an initial approximation or trial function.

With above correction functional stationary we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta u_{n+1}(x, t) &= \delta u_n(x, t) + \delta \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + u_n(x, \xi) - 2u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi, \\ \delta u_{n+1}(x, t) &= \delta u_n(x, t) \delta \int_0^t \lambda(\xi) \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} \right) d\xi, \\ \delta u_{n+1}(x, t) &= \delta u_n(x, t) (1 + \lambda(\xi)) - \delta \int_0^t \lambda'(\xi) u_n(x, \xi) d\xi, \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

By using the following stationary conditions:

$$\delta u_n : 1 + \lambda(\xi) = 0, \quad (4.5)$$

$$\delta u_n : \lambda'(\xi) = 0, \quad (4.6)$$

This gives the Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(\xi) = -1$, therefore the following iteration formula becomes as:

$$u_{n+1}(x, t) = u_n(x, t) - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_n(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + u_n(x, \xi) - 2u_n^2(x, \xi) + u_n^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi \quad (4.7)$$

We can select $u_0(x, y) = \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}$, from the given condition.

Using this selection into the Eq. (4.7), the following successive approximation can be obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_0(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}, \\
u_1(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}} - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_0(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_0(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + u_0(x, \xi) - 2u_0^2(x, \xi) + u_0^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi \\
&= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2} t \\
u_2(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2} t \\
&\quad - \int_0^t \left(\frac{\partial u_1(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi} - \frac{\partial^2 u_1(x, \xi)}{\partial x^2} + u_1(x, \xi) - 2u_1^2(x, \xi) + u_1^3(x, \xi) \right) d\xi \\
&= - \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{6 \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)} \left(2 \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) - 6 \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2 + 5 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2 \right) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2} - \frac{1}{8} \frac{\left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^3} \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) t^2 \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{12} \frac{\left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} - 2e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^5} t^3 \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{32} \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^3 \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^3}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^6} t^4
\end{aligned} \tag{4.8}$$

As a result, the series of the exact solution of the Eq. (4.1) can be constructed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_n(x, t) &= - \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{6 \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)} \left(2 \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) - 6 \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2 + 5 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2 \right) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2} - \frac{1}{8} \frac{\left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^3} \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right) t^2 \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{12} \frac{\left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2 \left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} - 2e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^2}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^5} t^3 + \frac{1}{32} \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^3 \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^3}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} \right)^6} t^4 \\
&\quad + \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

Using the identity,

$$u(x, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n(x, t), \quad (4.10)$$

We can write Eq. (4.9) in the closed form as:

$$v(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x - \frac{t}{4}} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x + \frac{t}{4}}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x - \frac{t}{4}} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x + \frac{t}{4}}} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \tanh\left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(x - \frac{t}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right) \quad (4.11)$$

This is the exact solution of the problem, Eq. (4.1).

4.2. The homotopy perturbation method:

We construct a homotopy for Eq. (4.1) in the following form:

$$H(v, p) = (1 - p) \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} \right] + p \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} - v(1 - v)(v - 1) \right]. \quad (4.12)$$

The solution of Eq. (4.1) can be written as a power series in p as:

$$v = v_0 + p v_1 + p^2 v_2 + \dots \quad (4.13)$$

Substituting Eq. (4.13) and Eq. (4.2) into Eq. (4.12) and equating the terms with identical powers of p :

$$\begin{aligned} p^0: \quad \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t}, & v_0(x, 0) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}, \\ p^1: \quad \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial^2 v_0}{\partial x^2} + v_0(1 - v_0)(v_0 - 1), & v_1(x, 0) &= 0, \\ p^2: \quad \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial^2 v_1}{\partial x^2} + 4v_0v_1 - v_1 - 3v_1v_0^2, & v_2(x, 0) &= 0, \\ p^3: \quad \frac{\partial v_3}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial^2 v_2}{\partial x^2} + 4v_0v_2 - v_2 - 3v_2v_0^2 + 2v_1^2 - 3v_0v_1^2, & v_3(x, 0) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4.14)$$

Using the Maple package to solve recursive sequences, Eq. (4.14), we obtain the followings:

$$\begin{aligned} v_0(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}, \\ v_1(x, t) &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2} t, \\ v_2(x, t) &= -\frac{1}{8} \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^3} t^2, \\ v_3(x, t) &= -\frac{1}{48} \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2 - 4 + \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^4} t^3, \end{aligned} \quad (4.15)$$

By setting $p = 1$ in Eq. (4.13) the solution of Eq. (4.1) can be obtained as $v = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 +$

...Therefore the solution of Eq. (4.1) is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} v(x, t) &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2} t - \frac{1}{8} \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^3} t^2 - \frac{1}{48} \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2 - 4 + \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^4} t^3 \\ &+ \dots \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

The Taylor series expansion for $\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x - \frac{t}{4}} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x + \frac{t}{4}}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x - \frac{t}{4}} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x + \frac{t}{4}}}\right)$ is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x - \frac{t}{4}} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x + \frac{t}{4}}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x - \frac{t}{4}} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x + \frac{t}{4}}} \\ &= \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2} t - \frac{1}{8} \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^3} t^2 \\ & - \frac{1}{48} \frac{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2 - 4 + \left(e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^2}{\left(e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x}\right)^4} t^3 \\ & + \dots \end{aligned} \tag{4.17}$$

Combining Eq. (4.17) with Eq. (4.16), we get as follow:

$$v(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x - \frac{t}{4}} - e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x + \frac{t}{4}}}{e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x - \frac{t}{4}} + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x + \frac{t}{4}}} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \tan h\left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(x - \frac{t}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right), \tag{4.18}$$

This is the exact solution of the problem, Eq. (4.1).

4.3. Comparison

In order to compare accuracy of the obtained results by VIM and HPM, Table 1 is presented. Table1 shows the trend of rapid convergence of the results of $S_1(x, t) = u_0(x, t)$ to $S_6(x, t) = u_5(x, t)$ by using the VIM and $S_1(x, t) = v_0(x, t)$ to $S_6(x, t) = \sum_{i=0}^5 v_i(x, t)$ by using the HPM.

		percentage of relative error (%RE)					
		x = 1		x = 2		x = 3	
		VIM	HPM	VIM	HPM	VIM	HPM
t = 0.1	$S_1(x, t)$	0.02048339234	0.01693168743	0.01405218794 2	0.01002710463	0.0049103256 34	0.00548815042 4
	$S_3(x, t)$	0.0000372193	0.00000233734 6256	0.00000014038 4	2.025644856e-7	3.006402347e- 7	9.527700575 e-7
	$S_5(x, t)$	3.05039471 e- 10	2.153484215 e- 10	3.673469731e- 10	3.464089104e-10	3.900085184e- 11	3.155246333e- 10
	$S_6(x, t)$	3.464089104e- 11	9.744801271e- 12	6.93056448e- 12	3.920421861e-11	5.310645210e- 12	9.937961084 e-11
t = 0.3	$S_1(x, t)$	0.0479201486	0.05344388963	0.0340651212	0.03164997413	0.0195298765	0.01732302882
	$S_3(x, t)$	0.000053893210 7	0.00006806597 676	0.00000295134 9	0.000003967422 423	0.0000175933 129	0.00002580410 708
	$S_5(x, t)$	6.6789957862 e-7	6.184344787 e- 8	8.82016354 e-8	9.467317545 e-8	6.320132452 e-9	5.516785201 e-8
	$S_6(x, t)$	1.005127657 e- 9	1.008793018 e- 8	1.0032766804 e-10	1.166422821 e-9	2.0057247916 e-10	2.026398250 e-9
t = 0.4	$S_1(x, t)$	0.06327865268	0.07311570399	0.0579320112	0.04329980772	0.0270445322	0.02369935005
	$S_3(x, t)$	0.0000839203	0.00016754105 15	0.00005833244	0.000007498069 748	0.0000387652	0.00006123279 256
	$S_5(x, t)$	7.540283747e-7	2.799248652e-7	5.33058374e-8	4.009848425e-7	2.329096851e- 8	2.364525175 e-7
	$S_6(x, t)$	7.756355434 e- 7	5.775483086 e- 8	8.234294012 e- 9	6.758498122 e-9	3.143458570 e-9	1.111128458 e-8

Table 1 shows: the percentage of relative errors of the results of $S_1(x, t) = u_0(x, t)$ to $S_6(x, t) = u_5(x, t)$ by using the VIM and $S_1(x, t) = v_0(x, t)$ to $S_6(x, t) = \sum_{i=0}^5 v_i(x, t)$ by using the HPM.

Deng [19] obtained some travelling solitary wave solutions of Eq. (1.1) by applying the first-integral method as follows.

$$v(x, t) = \left[\frac{\gamma}{2} \pm \frac{\gamma}{2} \tanh \left(\frac{n\gamma(\rho \mp \alpha)}{4(n+1)} \left[x - \frac{(\alpha \mp \rho)\gamma + (\alpha \pm \rho)(n+1)}{2(n+1)} t + x_0 \right] \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{n}}, \quad (4.19)$$

Where

$$\rho = \sqrt{\alpha^2 + 4\beta(1+n)} \text{ and } x_0 \text{ arbitrary constant.} \quad (4.20)$$

This is in full agreement of the closed form solutions of Eq. (4.11) and Eq. (4.18) obtained by the VIM and HPM respectively for selected value of parameters $\alpha, \eta, \lambda, n, \gamma, \beta,$

4. Conclusion

In the present research work, the exact solution of the Burgers - Huxley nonlinear diffusion equation is obtained by using the VIM and HPM. The validity and effectiveness of the VIM and HPM are shown by solving the non-homogenous non-linear differential equations and the very rapid convergence to the exact solutions is numerically demonstrated. In order to show their accuracy and reliability in solving the equation, a comparison between obtained results by the methods is presented. As shown in the Table 1, the maximum relative error of less than 0.000078% and 0.0000058% are achieved by using the VIM and HPM respectively. The results proved that the methods are effective and powerful algorithm with acceptable accuracy in order to obtain the exact solution of nonlinear differential equations.

5. References

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